

1st TwINSol-CECs Workshop

**Advance multicomponent analyses and novel solutions
for protection of environmental resources
with contaminants of emerging concern in focus**

Book of Abstracts

**University of Novi Sad
Faculty of Technology Novi Sad
Novi Sad, Serbia**

20-21 October 2022

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

1st TwiNSol-CECs Workshop

Advance multicomponent analyses and novel solutions for protection of environmental resources with contaminants of emerging concern in focus

**University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technology Novi Sad (TFNS), Novi Sad, Serbia,
20-21 October 2022**

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Dear colleagues, participants of the 1st TwiNSol-CECs Workshop,

On behalf of the TwiNSol-CECs team I would like to welcome you all to the first event in a series of events planned within the TwiNSol-CECs project (GA 101059867). I would also like to thank you for all of your contributions in the form of oral and poster presentations, with the abstracts gathered in this Book of Abstracts accessible via the project website (www.twinsol-cec.com). We are really proud to have won this project in the framework of Horizon Europe and honoured to have this and many more opportunities to share knowledge and exchange ideas within the domain of environmental research.

The aim of this event is to gather scientists and experts interested in, but not limited to, problems of contaminants of emerging concern (CECs) occurrence in the environment and relevant analytical methods, as well as novel solutions for their removal. The Workshop will also go beyond these topics as it will serve as a forum for exchange of project ideas and results in the domain of environmental protection, contributing to the harmonization of research and innovation efforts important for the sustainable transition of whole Europe, as foreseen by the European Green Deal, towards zero-pollution, i.e. toxic free environment. A session dedicated to the ongoing EU funded Twinning projects at the Serbian universities is a part of the Workshop agenda, in addition to the presentations of the scientific results of the registered participants. The session is of two-fold importance: to share information on the latest research developments in Serbia, recognized as “excellence pockets” by the European Commission, and to promote the Twinning calls as a way of boosting institutional research capacities.

TwiNSol-CECs team wishes you all a pleasant stay in Novi Sad, hoping for fruitful discussions on new research ideas and collaboration for better toxic-free common future,

Prof. Dr. Nataša Đurišić-Mladenović
Chair

PROGRAM

1st TwiNSol-CECs Workshop

Advance multicomponent analyses and novel solutions for protection of environmental resources with contaminants of emerging concern in focus

University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technology Novi Sad (TFNS), Novi Sad, Serbia,
20-21 October 2022

Agenda

20 Oct 2022

9,00-15,00 Registration at the Faculty of Technology Novi Sad, Entrance Hall (Bulevar cara Lazara 1)

Joint morning session of the 1st TwiNSol-CECs Workshop and 2nd ICAPP,
University of Novi Sad Rectorate building, Amphitheater (Dr Zorana Đinđića 1)

10,45-12,15 Official opening

Plenary lectures

12,15-12,45 João G. Crespo: **Membranes in Bioprocessing**

12,30-13,00 *Coffee break*

13,00-13,30 Marinella Farré, Marta Llorca, Katerina Savva, Albert Vega: **The challenge of assessing contaminants of emerging concern in the environment**

13,30-14,00 *TwINSol-CECs Networking with coffee* – Exploring further project endeavours

14,00-15,00 *Lunch break*

Afternoon session, Faculty of Technology, Blue Hall (Bulevar cara Lazara 1)

Invited lectures on TWINNING projects in domain of environmental research

Chairs: Vladimir Beškoski and Nataša Đurišić-Mladenović

- 15,00-15,20 Nataša Đurišić-Mladenović, Zita Šereš, Biljana Pajin, Jelena Živančev, Nikola Maravić, Igor Antić, TFNS: **Twinning for excellence in protection of environmental resources: TwiNSol-CECs**
- 15,20-15,40 Biljana Basarin, Faculty of Science, Novi Sad: **EXTREMECLIMTWIN – Extremely important linking for excellence in hydroclimate research**
- 15,40-16,00 Snežana Maletić, Faculty of Science, Novi Sad: **Twinning excellence on organic soil amendments effect on nutrient and contaminant dynamics in the subsurface, TwinSubDyn**
- 16,00-16,20 Vladimir Beškoski, Faculty of Chemistry, Belgrade: **Twinning to address the PFAS challenge in Serbia – PFAStwin**
- 16,20-16,35 *Coffee break*
- 16,35-16,55 Đurđa Kerkez, Faculty of Science, Novi Sad: **Twinning for smart water – thinking and rethinking wastewater management in circular economy frame (SmartWaterTwin)**
- 16,55-17,15 Dragana Miladinović, Ankica Kondić-Špika, Tijana Zeremski, Sandra Cvejić, Sonja Gvozdenac, Boško Dedić, Siniša Jocić, Aleksandra Radanović, Ana Marjanović-Jeromela, et al., Institute of Field and Vegetable Crops, National Institute of Republic of Serbia, Novi Sad: Institute of Field and Vegetable Crops: **CROPINNO - Stepping up scientific excellence and innovation capacity for climate-resilient crop improvement and production**

Invited lectures on topics of TwiNSol-CECs interest

Chairs: Jelena Živančev and Vesna Vasić

- 17,15-17,40 Szabolcs Kertész, Gabriella Huszár, Balázs Szegedi, József R. Lennert, József Csanádi, Nikolett Sz. Gulyás, Zsuzsanna László, Gábor Veréb, Sándor Beszédes, Cecilia Hodúr, **Opportunities and challenges for membrane separation process intensification**

Oral presentation of registered participants

- 17,40-17,55 Marija B. Lješević, Branka D. Lončarević, Vladimir P. Beškoski, **Application of respirometry and comprehensive two-dimensional gas chromatography in biodegradation studies**

21 Oct 2022

- 9,00-10,00 Registration at the Faculty of Technology Novi Sad, Entrance Hall (Bulevar cara Lazara 1)
- Morning session, Faculty of Technology, Blue Hall** (Bulevar cara Lazara 1)
Invited lectures on topics of TwINSol-CECs interest
Chairs: Marijana Dragosavac and Ivica Strelec
- 10,00-10,25 Jelena Živančev, Igor Antić, Maja Buljovčić, Dušan Rakić, Nataša Đurišić-Mladenović, **Analysis of CECs in the environment of Western Balkans**
- 10,25-10,50 Sanja Panić, Mirjana Petronijević, Nataša Đurišić-Mladenović: **The development strategies for nano-engineered heterogeneous catalysts for wastewater treatment – towards greener approach**
- 10,50-11,15 Sandra Budžaki, Zita Šereš, Ivica Strelec: **Immobilization of lipases on functionalised carriers produced from selected agro-food industrial waste**
- 11,15-11,30 *Coffee break*
- 11,30-11,55 Nikola Maravić, Zita Šereš, Biljana Pajin, Dragana Šoronja Simović, Nataša Đurišić-Mladenović, Jelena Šurlan, **Membrane technologies in water treatment**
- 11,55-12,20 Vesna Vasić, Dragana Kukić, Marina Šćiban: **Biomaterials in water and wastewater treatment**
- Oral presentation of registered participants
- 12,20-12,35 Marijana Dragosavac, **Bespoke particles for purification and separation manufactured via membrane emulsification**
- 12,35-12,50 Dragana, B. Ljubojević Pelić, Nikolina, J, Novakov, Brankica, D, Kartalović, Jelena, M, Vranešević, Miloš, M, Pelić, Željko, A, Mihaljev, Milica, M. Živkov Baloš, **Emerging contaminants in aquatic ecosystem and their effects on fish and human health through the food web**
- 12,50-13,05 Nikolina, J. Novakov, Brankica, D, Kartalović, Dragana, B, Ljubojević Pelić, Jelena, M, Vranešević, Miloš, M, Pelić, **Use of purified wastewater from slaughterhouse and farm industries in aquaculture and agriculture**
- 13,05-14,30 *Lunch break*
- Afternoon session, Faculty of Technology, Central Lobby** (Bulevar cara Lazara 1)
- 14,30-16,30 Poster presentations with coffee (set-up 11,15-11,40, dismantling: 16,30-17,00)
- P1** ANALYSIS OF BIODEGRADATION PRODUCTS FROM BIOPLASTICS BY LC-HRMS,
Katerina Savva, Maria Fernandez-Altamira, Maria Vila, Marinella Farré, Marta Llorca
- P2** SYNTHESIS AND CHARACTERIZATION OF MAGNETITE-BIOCHAR COMPOSITE AS A POTENTIAL ADSORBENT FOR WASTEWATER TREATMENT,
Mirjana Petronijević, Sanja Panić, Saša Savić, Sanja Petrović, Nataša Đurišić-Mladenović

- P3** APPLICABILITY OF LIFE CYCLE IMPACT ASSESSMENT METHODOLOGIES: DESIGN OF NATURE BASED SOLUTIONS FOR WATER DECONTAMINATION,
Sanja Radovic, Maja Turk Sekulic, Sabolc Pap, Boris Agarski, Djordje Vukelic, Jelena Radonic, Jelena Prodanovic
- P4** IS THERE A SHARP DIFFERENCE BETWEEN THE DEFINITIONS “COMPOUNDS OF EMERGING CONCERNS” AND “ENDOCRINE-DISRUPTING COMPOUNDS”?
Igor Antić, Jelena Živančev, Maja Buljovčić, Dušan Rakić, Nataša Đurišić-Mladenović
- P5** OCCURRENCE AND FATE OF PHARMACEUTICALS IN SPANISH INTERMITTENT STREAMS,
Olga Gómez-Navarro, Nicola Montemurro, Sandra Pérez
- P6** PRESENCE OF CECs IN CROPS AFTER IRRIGATION WITH CONTAMINATED WATER USING HRMS,
Nicola Montemurro, Sandra Perez Solsona
- P7** BLACKBERRY STEM LIGNIN AS A BIOSORBENT FOR REMOVAL OF Cr(VI) IONS FROM WASTEWATER,
Vesna, M. Vasić, Dragana V. Kukić, Marina B. Šćiban, Mirjana G. Antov, Jorge Gominho, Ana Lourenço, Ricardo A. Costa, Duarte M. Neiva
- P8** MICROPLASTICS AS A VECTOR OF POLLUTION WITH PERSISTENT ORGANIC POLLUTANTS,
Brankica D.Kartalovic, Jelena M. Vranešević, Dušan S.Lazic, Nikolina J. Novakov, Krešimir M. Mastanjević, Kristina J. Habschied
- P9** WATER REGULATIONS, TREATMENT OF INDUSTRIAL WASTEWATER AND PROBLEMS IN PRACTICE, Žužana Šandor Milošević
- P10** PAHs ORIGINATING FROM TRADITIONAL SMOKEHOUSES AND THEIR EFFECT ON ENVIRONMENT AND HUMAN HEALTH,
Jelena M. Vranešević, Brankica D. Kartalović, Nikolina J. Novakov, Snezana Škaljac, Suzana L. Vidaković Knežević, Miloš M. Pelić, Dragana B. Ljubojević Pelić
- P11** APPLICATION OF ORGANIC ACTIVATED BENTONITE IN THE TREATMENT OF AMMONIA-PHENOL WASTEWATER,
Hana Alihodžić, Abdel Đozić, Melisa Ahmetović, Indira Šestan, Sabina Begić, Mirnesa Zohorović, Halid Junuzović
- P12** APPLICATION OF RAW BENTONITE IN THE TREATMENT OF AMMONIA-PHENOL WASTEWATER,
Abdel Đozić, Hana Alihodžić, Halid Junuzović, Indira Šestan, Sabina Begić, Mirnesa Zohorović, Melisa Ahmetović

16,30-16,45 Certificate awarding and concluding remarks (Blue Hall)

TWINNING EXCELLENCE ON ORGANIC SOIL AMENDMENTS EFFECT ON NUTRIENT AND CONTAMINANT DYNAMICS IN THE SUBSURFACE, TwinSubDyn

Snežana SM. Maletić

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TwinSubDyn aims to establish a research knowledge hub at University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Sciences (UNSPMF), Serbia, on the impacts of organic soil amendments on the fate of contaminant, and nutrient dynamics in the soil subsurface and implications for groundwater quality. The project will significantly boost research and innovation capacities of UNSPMF, through a twinning action with internationally leading research institutions in this research field from Europe: University of Vienna (UNIVIE), Forschungszentrum Jülich GmbH (FZJ), Martin Luther University Halle-Wittenberg (MLU) and Instituto de Recursos Naturales y Agrobiología de Sevilla (IRNAS-CSIC). The strategy for stepping up and stimulating scientific excellence and innovation capacity for our TwinSubDyn defined research topic is based on: Networking for Excellence, Establishment of long-lasting strategic partnerships with leading European research organizations; Raising the EU and global research profile of UNSPMF and its staff, Development of Science and Innovation Strategy, Spreading scientific knowledge; and finally Increasing overall competence via the strategic collaborative consortium TwinSubDyn research project and its intrinsic knowledge exchange and gains.

Keywords: Environment, Soil, Groundwater, Organic Amendments

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